

Interview Guide

AI Alignment Interview Study

Part 1: Explain about the NextG2Com initiative

- This study is conducted in the context of a new competence center in future advanced communication systems, which is a collaboration between Lund University, industry partners and public actors.
- This initiative will continue for the next ten years, and one of the goals of the study is to initiate collaboration and learn more about the participating companies' goals and challenges.
- The purpose of this study is exploring AI alignment risks and identifying key metrics for continuous monitoring and testing of such risks.

Part 2: Ask for the consent (summarizing the consent form)

Asking their consent to record the interview and restating that:

- Your participation is entirely voluntary;
- You are free to refuse to answer any question;
- You are free to withdraw at any time;
- Information will be anonymized to prevent conclusions about the identity of the persons or companies involved.

Part 3: Perform the interview

Part 3.1: Demographics

- (1) What is your current role within the organization?
- (2) What previous roles have you been in? In which industries or sectors have you primarily worked?
- (3) What is your educational background?
- (4) How much experience do you have working directly with AI technologies or AI-related projects?
- (5) Have you been involved in any discussions or initiatives related to AI risks, ethics, governance, or policy-making?

Part 3.2: AI enabled products or services used/envisioned in their organization

Terminology:

- AI alignment aims to make AI systems behave in line with human intentions and values. As AI systems grow more capable, so do risks from misalignment.

- The AI alignment problem is the challenge of building AI systems such that they do what their stakeholders want them to do. Misalignment occurs when the AI systems perform differently, unexpected to what is desired from the stakeholders' values.
- Risks for misalignment are prevalent both pre and post deployment and may have severe consequences for individuals, organizations and society.
- Use-cases:
 - Amazon's (AI-powered) recruiting tool penalized resumes that mentioned the terms of "women" or "women's", thus; exposing gender discrimination towards female candidates.
 - Google Photos automatically tagging black couple as being "gorillas", which have been reported as racist and unacceptable.
 - Deceptive Alignment & Manipulation (e.g. current large language models occasionally generate inaccurate or suboptimal responses despite having the capacity to provide more accurate answers, systems that can persuade individuals to take action that may lead to hazardous outcomes, recommender systems (where the system influences the users' preferences)) .
 - Collectively Harmful Behaviors (AI systems have the potential to take actions that are seemingly benign in isolation but become problematic in multi-agent or societal contexts.)

Questions:

- (6) In your work experience, do you design AI enabled products, or development processes supported by AI?
 - (if yes, follow-up) what kind of?
 - Example: Predictive Maintenance in Manufacturing: AI algorithms, when integrated into Cyber Physical Systems, can analyze real-time data from sensors embedded in machinery to predict when equipment is likely to fail.
- (7) Also, what type of AI services do you use for accomplishing your tasks?
 - For instance, for developers, use of AI in code review, or using internal AI enabled chat portal, or issue/bug management. For managers, tools related to productivity, statistical analysis/dashboards.

Part 3.3: AI alignment and associated misalignment risks

* Show the EU ethical guidelines and risks taxonomy correspondingly

- (8) There are seven ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI. Pick one or two which you think are the most important for the AI systems/ products you work with or design?
 - Follow up on this – Are those guidelines being focused and worked upon?
- (9) Also, which ones do you think are the most challenging for the AI systems/ products you work with or design?
- (10) Which alignment risks do you foresee in your context when you see this taxonomy?

Part 3.4: Factors and types of AI misalignment risks

Terminology:

- Double edge components are designed to enhance the capability of AI systems in handling real-world settings but also potentially exacerbate misalignment issues.
- One of the examples of double edge components is **situational awareness**. Knowing the situation can help the model better understand human intent, finish tasks within its ability, and search for outlier help if needed. However, such knowledge also paves the way for advanced methods of reward hacking and heightened deception skills to chase instrumental subgoals.
- **Double edge components** -> misalignment behaviors
 - Situational awareness
 - Broadly scoped goals
 - Mesa-Optimization Objectives
 - Access to Increased Resources
- Some of the misalignment behaviors of double edge components are as follows:
 - **Power-Seeking Behaviors** to achieve optimization objective (e.g. manipulating the market)
 - **Untruthful Output** (e.g. LLM hallucination, sometimes intentional)
 - **Violation of Ethics** (Unethical behaviors in AI systems pertain to actions that counteract the common good or breach moral standards – such as those causing harm to others)
 - **Deceptive Alignment & Manipulation** (e.g. current large language models occasionally generate inaccurate or suboptimal responses despite having the capacity to provide more accurate answers, systems that can persuade individuals to take action that may lead to hazardous outcomes, recommender systems (where the system influences the users' preferences))
 - **Collectively Harmful Behaviors** (AI systems have the potential to take actions that are seemingly benign in isolation but become problematic in multi-agent or societal contexts.)

Questions:

- (11) What do you think are the primary factors contributing to AI misalignment in your context? (refer to DE components but encourage creativity)
- (12) What would you expect as nature of the caused misalignment behavior? (refer to misalignment behaviors listed above)

Part 3.5: Alignment governance/Monitoring & Testing metrics

- (13) Based on your experience, how do you think your organization can work to test and monitor existing misalignment risks with the AI products or services being used?

Part 3.6: Conclusion

(14) Would you like to share or add anything else?

(15) Is there anyone else you know who would be a suitable interview partner?

Thanks for your time, and we would like to inform you that the transcript from the interview will be returned for review once the post processing has been done to remove any form of errors.